

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN AS A SCIENTIFIC PROBLEM.

Abdullajonova Nargizakhan

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi
1st year master's student majoring in "Music Education and Art".

Trigulova Adelya Khusainovna

Supervisor:

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

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The problem of development of creative abilities is multidimensional and difficult. At present, both in psychology and pedagogy, there are different points of view about the nature and concept of abilities. The problem of creativity aims us at an activity that creates something new that did not exist before. It is characterized by uniqueness and it is characterized not by the result with its quality, but by active creative productivity. "Creativity is the ability to be surprised and learn, the ability to find a solution in non-standard situations, it is a focus on discovering something new and the ability to deeply understand one's experience".¹ A teacher from Kazan, V. Andreev, gives the following definition: "creativity is one of the types of human activity aimed at resolving a contradiction (solving a creative problem), creativity requires objective (social, material) and subjective personal conditions (knowledge, skills, creative abilities), the results of creativity have novelty and originality, personal and social significance, as well as progressiveness.

This definition combines not only the direction of creativity, but also its condition and result. An analysis of the interpretations of creativity by various scientists allowed us to identify the characteristic features of creativity: interactivity, as a quality of a person, as a productive activity that transforms reality. Speaking of a creative person, we are necessarily talking about her active life position, and this person necessarily has certain creative abilities.

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, abilities mean the rapid acquisition of knowledge and skills and their effective use in practice.

B. Teplov notes individual abilities as psychological characteristics that characterize each person and ensure successful activity. Great success in music is ensured by a good memory, synchronism in hand movements, an ear for music, and a sense of rhythm. Creativity is manifested in the ability to go beyond the limits of the tasks that are set. A certain creative activity determines the quality of abilities. Allocate sports, musical, artistic abilities, there are mathematical, literary, linguistic abilities.

Each type of activity involves a certain range of abilities. So special musical abilities, without which it is impossible to express oneself brightly, are: ear for music, both melodic and harmonic. Without it, the correct perception of music is impossible. The ear for music determines the modal feeling, which is also important for determining the character and mood of the work. A musical rhythm, without which it is impossible to perform a piece of music, both on a musical instrument and vocally. Only this ability determines the

¹ Алиев Ю.Б. Настольная книга школьного учителя – музыканта. – М.: гум. Изд. Центр ВЛАДОС, 2002. – 336 с.

responsiveness to the genre diversity of music. So when listening to a march, waltz, polonaise, mazurka, chorale, this ability helps to understand the genre of a musical work, its character, mood.

Indicators of the formation of creative abilities and productivity of thinking are memory, attention and imagination. The ability to analyze, generalize in the process of complex mental activity is also an indicator of a high level of thinking.

Creative abilities are manifested in creative activity, carry a degree of novelty and have personal and social value significance.

Modern psychological science denies the position on the connection between creative abilities and the level of intelligence. And the lessons of musical culture require general musical abilities to determine the mode, rhythm, form. These abilities are manifested in active creative activity.

This activity is manifested in the active perception of musical works studied at school and which are of great value in the world musical culture. Musicality is manifested in this activity as a whole complex of abilities necessary for successful musical activity. We distinguish the following types of musicality: musical perception and musical creativity.

Creative activity is manifested in the dynamics of the acquisition and use of knowledge, skills and abilities, and its important condition is development. As a result of creative activity, an individual perception of the surrounding world is carried out by a person. According to S.L. Rubinstein and A.N. Leontiev, activity is most often represented by the following components: needs, motives, actions, conditions, operations, results. The activity must necessarily have a goal defined by a motive, carried out in a certain way aimed at the result, which should be something original, new, unusual.

However, notes L.G. Vyatkin, not everything new can be defined as “creative”, but only “what should be socially personally significant, useful”². The novelty of creative activity is subjective and depends on the personality of the creator. A huge role in the process of creative activity in the educational process is played by the modernization of the ways of organizing this process, aimed at mastering the knowledge, skills and abilities of students. Thus, creativity in educational activities involves the introduction of a new, effective, aimed at optimizing the educational process. At the lessons of musical culture, this, of course, is the performance by the teacher on a musical instrument of a work at a high, professional level, as a result of which schoolchildren see the beauty of the work, its deep content and, of course, the professionalism of the teacher, who is able to convey to the students with his performance the uniqueness of the musical image, embedded in this piece of music.

Listening to works from the world musical classics in video performance by the stars of world culture, such tasks as observation, evaluation and memorization of these works are also effectively solved. As a result of a creative approach, students will learn the classics of world opera music, symphony orchestra performers, outstanding pianists, violinists, conductors, etc. All this can be carried out only as a result of the creative activity of the teacher, aimed at improving the quality of teaching at school and the quality of knowledge acquisition by schoolchildren.

² Андреев В.И. Диалектика воспитания и самовоспитания творческой личности. – Изд-во Каз. Ун-та, 1988. – 239 с.

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